

Master Thesis “Role of Generative Artificial Intelligence in modern management consulting industry and its impact on the future”

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of generative artificial intelligence (GAI) on the management consulting industry, focusing on the integration of GAI technologies within consulting firms and consultants' perspectives on its current and future influence. Conducted through 21 interviews across various global regions and consulting firms, the research captures a snapshot of GAI's developmental state within the sector. The findings indicate that many established consultancies have not fully embraced GAI, often lagging in adoption, strategic incorporation, and workforce re-skilling. Ethical usage, maintaining client trust, and the potential undermining of professional credibility also emerge as significant challenges.

Persistent GAI applications include research, data collection, various writing tasks, brainstorming, idea generation, and synthesizing information from a variety of documents. While the productivity gains from GAI use are modest at managerial levels, they are notably higher among analysts. The study also explores diverse viewpoints on the consulting industry's future in the wake of GAI's rise, highlighting the risks and transformative potential of the technology as well as personal concerns about job security among consultants.

This research contributes to understanding the evolving landscape of management consulting in response to GAI, offering insights for industry stakeholders aiming to navigate and leverage these technological shifts effectively.

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1. Introduction

“Predicting is very difficult, especially if it is about the future!”. This quote is often attributed to the famous physicist Niels Bohr, and it's intriguing to observe its resonance across various domains of human life. The development of technologies, especially Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), has long been considered an existential threat to numerous jobs. In 2013 and subsequently in 2017, Oxford researchers Frey and Osborne concluded that 47 percent of jobs in the United States were at 'high risk' of automation within the next 10 to 20 years (Frey & Osborne, 2017). This seminal paper, cited over 14,000 times as of January 2024, has become a pivotal academic reference regarding the potential impact of AI on employment. Several governments, including those of Australia, Finland, Norway, the UK, Germany, and Japan, used this study to formulate predictions of job losses (Coelli & Borland, 2019). Despite the gloomy outlook presented by Frey and Osborne, subsequent impactful studies, such as the OECD's "Automation, skills use, and training," have provided a more optimistic perspective. The OECD study, using different methodologies to assess the "automability of each task within a given job," suggests that only 14% of jobs in 32 countries are highly vulnerable, defined as having at least a 70% chance of automation (OECD, 2018)

Discrepancies between these studies not only exist in the share of "highly vulnerable" jobs but also in identifying which jobs are at the greatest risk. While Frey and Osborne primarily identified "white-collar" jobs, such as Telemarketers, Title Examiners, and Insurance Agents, as at risk, the OECD study highlights blue-collar jobs like Food Preparation Assistants, Cleaners and Helpers, and Laborers in mining and manufacturing. Despite these differences, both studies suggest that certain tasks resist automation, particularly those involving human social intelligence, cognitive abilities, and perception and manipulation skills in areas such as management, business, and finance.

However, these discussions were pre-2023. Since the release of ChatGPT by OpenAI in November 2022 and its immense popularity (100 million active users in just two months (Reuters, 2023a)), humanity has truly entered the age of generative AI (hence referred to as

GAI). AI has become the most discussed technology globally, with individual AI searches surging and AI earning a place on the "word of the year" lists at Oxford, Cambridge, and Merriam-Webster (Techcrunch, 2023). In the business world, more than \$40 billion in venture capital flowed into AI firms in the first half of 2023 (The Economist, 2023d) and there was an all-time high number of mentions of "AI" during earning calls of S&P 500 companies (The Economist, 2023c).

ChatGPT, as a powerful language model (LLM), answers questions and generate output from prompts provided in natural language. ChatGPT has demonstrated the ability to perform a variety of tasks previously believed to be the exclusive domain of human intelligence like write and review software code, summarize, reformulate text materials with different styles, create content for social media, handle routine tasks like responding emails, etc.(Ritala et al., 2024). ChatGPT is not only one tool available. Since its release and tremendous success, other tools and models began to emerge rapidly. Technological companies all over the world tried to develop and release ChatGPT-like products, able to answer any general question, such as Gemini by Google, Grok by X, Claude by Anthropic (all USA), Ernie by Baidu (China), Le-chat by Mistral (France), etc. At the same time, many smaller companies and startups have released domain-specific GAI products that focus on solving niche problems or tasks. According to AI aggregator TAAFT, there are more than 13 thousand different GAI tools solving more than 16 thousand different tasks. On the demand side, according to German online data platform Statista, the number of GAI users worldwide has exceeded 250 million in 2023.

GAI has already changed numerous businesses and jobs, as it is now perceived as a technology capable of handling many creative and complex tasks and with potential to be improved in the next years. In 2023, a growing body of research examined the potential impact of GAI on the future of humanity and its implications for the job market. Some of new studies were conducted by the consultancy McKinsey. One estimate suggests that GAI could add \$2.6 trillion to \$4.4 trillion annually to the global economy across various use cases, with about 75% of this value expected in customer operations, marketing and sales, software engineering, and R&D. GAI is poised to transform work dynamics by automating up to 70% of current work activities, especially in knowledge-intensive occupations involving decision-making and collaboration, areas previously deemed less susceptible to automation (McKinsey & Company, 2023c).

Another study focused on the U.S. job market suggests that activities accounting for up to 30% of currently worked hours could be automated by 2030 due to accelerated GAI use (McKinsey & Company, 2023a). Goldman Sachs provides similar estimates, suggesting that 25% of labor tasks could be automated within 10 years (Goldman Sachs, 2023). While McKinsey foresees GAI enhancing the work of STEM, creative, and business and legal professionals, it also anticipates the decline of employment in office support, customer service, and food service.

Another significant series of surveys, conducted by Katja Grace in 2016, 2021, and 2023 (after the release of ChatGPT), focused on top-tier AI researchers and their predictions about AI development and its impact on various aspects of human life, including job automation (Grace, 2022; Grace et al., 2018, 2024). These researchers estimate¹ with 90% probability that Truck Drivers and Retail Salespersons could be fully automated in 20 years, Surgeons in 50 years, and AI researchers in 100 years. The latest survey in 2023 reveals an interesting trend: researchers expect faster labor automation. For example, the chance of all human occupations becoming fully automatable is forecasted to reach 10% by 2037 and 50% as late as 2116 (compared to 2164 in the 2022 survey). Based on the latest survey of 2023, top 5 categories of existing occupations that are hardest to automate are “Computer and Mathematical”, “Life, Physical, and Social Science”, “Healthcare Practitioners and Technical”, “Management”, “Arts, Design, Entertainment, Sports, and Media”. Notably, respondents of 2016 and 2022 surveys also put “government and political jobs” as hardest to automate.

These predictions about the job market unequivocally suggest that there is no single job completely safe from automation. Even previously considered hard-to-automate jobs could be eroded or radically altered by AI. The author of this Master Thesis had around seven years of working experience in management consulting before starting the Master's in Digital Economy program. The AI developments of 2022-2023 prompted to ponder, "How is my profession changing? And what are the AI implications on management consulting in the future?" These questions served as the starting points for my research.

¹ Results are more-less the same for both 2016 and 2022 studies, similar findings of 2023 aren't published yet.

Already, there are signs that the professional services industry is evolving. McKinsey has partnered with Canadian AI firm Cohere to provide AI solutions to its clients (Reuters, 2023b). Bain & Company and Boston Consulting Group have announced partnerships with Open AI & Anthropic (Bain & Company, 2023; BCG, 2023a, 2023b). PwC US announced plans to invest 1 billion dollars over 3 years to “to expand and scale its artificial intelligence (AI) offerings and help clients reimagine their businesses through the power of generative AI”.(PwC, 2023). Deloitte as well as KPMG took another approach and rolled-out proprietary GAI chat bots “PairD” and “GenAI” for their employees (Financial Times, 2024; Forbes, 2023d).

At the same time, evidence collected in pre-GAI era by various consulting firms themselves about their clients reveals various challenges in adopting AI systems, as many companies reported minimal impact from their AI investments. It poses the question “Are management consultancies different from their clients in terms of GAI adoption?” This study would shed light on the details of how the management consulting industry is changing due to the development of GAI. How professional services firms plan to remain resilient and competitive in the age of GAI. How consultants in different countries and seniority levels are already being impacted by GAI development, and what they expect from the future of this technology.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1. What is generative artificial intelligence and status quo of technology development?

GAI has become so ubiquitous since 2022 that it might seem unnecessary to explain what exactly it is, especially since it's not the focus of this project to explain the nuts and bolts of the technological side of GAI. However, it feels important to at least briefly highlight what the technology is being discussed in the paper, how it works, what the capabilities and limitations of the technology are, and how it is being developed today.

GAI refers to a subset of artificial intelligence technology and designed to create (generate) content of various kinds including audio, code, images, text, and videos. Open AI, the pioneer of the technology and the company which developed the most discussed tool ChatGPT in 2022, described generative models as a type of unsupervised learning in AI that focuses on training models to generate new data similar to the data they were trained on (OpenAI, 2016). Since 2016, the field of GAI has evolved significantly, particularly with the gradual development of models like GPTs (Generative Pre-trained Transformers) and large language models (LLMs). These models are a subset of GAI, designed to generate human-like text by predicting the next word (token) in a sequence. They are trained on vast datasets and can generate coherent, contextually relevant text across various domains.

The evolution of Generative Pre-trained Transformers (GPT) showcases significant advancements in natural language processing. Initially introduced in 2018, GPT demonstrated the ability of generative language models to acquire knowledge and process dependencies unsupervised through pre-training on extensive datasets (Radford et al., 2018). In 2019, GPT-2 expanded this concept, enhancing the model's ability to translate text, answer questions, summarize passages, and generate coherent text sequences (Radford et al., 2019). The subsequent release of GPT-3 in 2020 marked a substantial scale-up in complexity, increasing the model's parameters from 1.5 billion in GPT-2 to 175 billion (OpenAI, 2020). The introduction of ChatGPT in 2022, a variant utilizing Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF), further refined the model's interaction capabilities, offering more human-like text

generation. The evolution culminated in GPT-4 in 2023, a model speculated to be trained with an unprecedented 100 trillion parameters, significantly enhancing its performance and establishing a new benchmark in AI-driven language understanding and generation (OpenAI et al., 2024). GPT and LLMs signify a shift towards more sophisticated, context-aware AI systems capable of large number of tasks. However it's evident that current models have limitations like hallucinations, providing unbiased answers, performing chain of actions without human intervention, maintaining context, common sense reasoning, planning etc. (OpenAI et al., 2024; Ray, 2023; Ritala et al., 2024). Whether or not these limitations could be resolved is an open question for next years as many companies continue to develop their models and improve its performance by including more training data, more parameters, optimizing speed and cost of training a model.

The research in AI domain in general but especially generative models, require significant human and financial resources to develop, train models and access vast amount of data. Hence it is dominated by corporations like OpenAI, Google, Meta and others which hire up to 70% individuals with PhD in AI domain in United States (Eastwood, 2023). Geographically speaking GAI research dominated by US companies and institutions as all top research models presented at major AI conferences were American. Chinese and European players are also competing however yet are behind in terms of both research and model's quality comparing to US. China's progress in GAI lags behind the US primarily due to limited access to diverse and voluminous data, exacerbated by language barriers and the closed nature of Chinese internet platforms. Additionally, U.S. export controls on critical hardware and a shortfall in expertise due to restricted talent flow further hinder China's ability to compete in developing foundational AI models (The Economist, 2023a). Europe's advancement in GAI is hindered by stringent regulatory measures, like the AI Act, which impact innovation dynamics, reduce investment levels, and emphasize ethical development over rapid technological deployment (European Union, 2023; McKinsey & Company, 2023b; Winters, 2023). The GAI sector is marked by robust competition and rapid innovation, with significant investments from US tech giants, as well as substantial funding directed towards startups, and government organizations. Despite individual successes, no single organization has established a definitive lead, as knowledge and advancements in AI technology are rapidly shared and integrated across the industry. This

environment fosters continual innovation, with all major players remaining within a narrow competitive margin of each other. (The Economist, 2023b; Thomas, 2024)

2.2. How has management consulting industry changed over its lifespan?

Cambridge Dictionary defines Management Consultancy as "a company that offers other companies advice about the best way of managing and improving their businesses." Greiner and Merzger defined management consulting as "an advisory service contracted for and provided to organizations by specially trained and qualified persons who assist, in an objective and independent manner, the client organization to identify management problems, analyze such problems, recommend solutions to these problems, and help, when requested, in the implementation of solutions" (Greiner & Metzger, 1983). McKenna provides other definition "Management consulting is the practice of providing consulting services to organizations to improve their performance or in any way to assist in achieving organizational objectives. Organizations may draw upon the services of management consultants for a number of reasons, including gaining external (and presumably objective) advice and accessing consultants' specialized expertise regarding concerns that call for additional oversight" (McKenna, 1995).

Management consulting (MC) industry emerged at the end of 19th century with the growth and rising complexity of the largest industrial organizations (2nd industrial revolution) in the United States. (McKenna, 1995). Professional services firms like Arthur D. Little, Booz Allen Hamilton, PwC, and Ernst & Young started operating, and in 1926, McKinsey & Company, the most renowned consultancy company, was founded.(McKinsey & Company, 2022). Since then, management consultants have remained in high demand, and estimates of the global consulting market size vary, with figures ranging from \$100 billion to \$280 billion. Management consulting as largest sub-segment of consulting market as expected to reach \$175,4 billion in 2026 according to Global Industry Analysts. European agency Consultancy.uk, suggested that only EU market size as 61 billion dollars in 2021. The industry attracts top talent from around the world. For example, a career in Strategy & Management Consulting is the top choice of graduates in the UK (Universum & Consultancy.uk, 2017). Number of Management consultants employed in US increased from 540 thousand in 2012 to 809 thousand in 2022, with compound

annual growth rate (CAGR) as 4% according to US Bureau of Labor Statistics. Part of the reason of such interest to management consulting from graduates is attractive compensation. According to recent study of 25 leading MC firms in US average salary of bachelor and master graduates is above \$100,000 per year, which is \$20,000 and \$10,000 more than on average can earn US bachelor or master graduates (National Association of Colleges and Employers, 2022).

The MC industry has weathered various shifts in the business world, such as the expansion of international trade, the rise of multinational companies, the advent of the internet, and the growth of outsourcing. Despite facing challenges like the Great Depression, the consequences of the Black Monday stock market crash in 1987, the global financial crisis of 2007-2008, and the COVID-19 pandemic, the MC industry has proven resilient. But what makes MC so resilient to changes of environment? Some general understanding of industry evolution would be helpful to understand whether GAI will wipe the MC anytime soon.

In a 2005 article, Erik Krell highlighted the remarkable performance of the management consulting industry since 1970, with continuous market growth until the 2001 recession, experiencing double-digit growth in 16 out of 18 years prior to the recession, often above 20% per year (Krell, 2005). The late 20th century was a prosperous period for consulting firms, marked by substantial billings and a surplus of projects. As a striking example of consulting success, in the period between 1989 and 1994, AT&T, the telecommunications incumbent in the US, alone spent half a billion dollars on consulting services, in some years more than the company spent on R&D (McKenna, 1995; O'Shea & Madigan, 1997).

In the early 2000s, several important events occurred that cast a shadow over the industry. The rapid growth of Internet business created a demand for a very different skill set from consultants: not just advice on what to do, but actual technological implementation of new software and business models. Obviously, new IT consultancies with a more technical focus (e.g. IBM, Accenture) emerged to solve new problems. And it took some time for classic MC firms to adapt and implement new practices like ERP (enterprise resource planning) and other efforts to handle large systems.

At the same time, there was a major debate about the independence of consulting firms and the issue of whether providing consulting services to public companies compromised the quality of the audits on which investors relied in making investment decisions. The culmination of this debate was the scandal surrounding the energy company Enron, the 6th largest public company in the U.S. in early 2001, and its bankruptcy on December 2, 2001, which happened after the U.S. SEC uncovered huge accounting manipulations (losses of \$591 million and debts of \$690 million) with the help of its auditing firm Arthur Andersen (Investopedia, 2023). This scandal had a profound and mixed effect on the consulting industry. On the one hand, the U.S. Congress passed the Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002, which, among other things, made it more difficult for consultants to provide certain services to their audit clients and increased scrutiny of consulting services, which is indeed a negative effect on business. As a result, some firms are "spinning off their MC business from audit (PwC is selling its business to IBM, KPMG is spinning off Bearing Point, Ernst & Young is selling its business to Capgemini) (AccountancyAge, 2015). On the other hand, traditional management consulting firms such as McKinsey & Company, Bain, BCG, and others benefited from the scandal as they were able to differentiate themselves from competitors as more transparent, independent, and innovative. As a result, the consulting industry is better positioned to serve the needs of its clients in the years to come.

This series of events in the early 2000s was probably the first major challenge for the MC industry, but after the initial shock of emerging competition from new-born technology consultancies and the separation of management consulting from the audit business (for a short time), MC firms continued to thrive.

The next big wave of discussion about the "future of consulting" came in the early 2010s. Duff McDonald, in his book "The Firm: The Story of McKinsey and Its Secret Influence on American Business," wrote in the epilogue, "The profession it largely invented [by McKinsey] is more hotly contested than ever before" (McDonald, 2014). At about the same time, in 2013, Harvard Business School professor Clayton Christensen wrote an article in HBR called "Consulting on the cusp of disruption." Christensen is the one who introduced or at least popularized the word "disruption" to the business world in his book "The Innovator's Dilemma" in 1997. So, before we dive into the "disruption of consulting," let's find out how Christensen defined disruptive technologies: "They ... have two important characteristics: First, they

typically offer a different set of performance attributes - ones that, at least initially, existing customers do not value. Second, the performance attributes that existing customers do value improve so rapidly that the new technology can later invade these established markets" (Christensen, 1997). Thus, technologies that met these criteria were disruptive, while others were merely sustaining because they enhanced existing products or services. In his 2013 article, Christensen argued that consulting hasn't changed much over the past 100 years: a few smart outsiders come in for a short engagement, try to answer some tough questions about the client's business, and then leave. Meanwhile, new business models and competitors emerge, and incumbents [MC firms] "choose to ignore the new players or flee to higher-margin activities." Christensen suggested that lack of change and "the same forces have disrupted many businesses, from steel to publishing". Christensen highlighted some specific causes of the coming industry disruption; however, the causes of disruption are not technological but rather organizational. He argued that the large number of MBA graduates filling strategy and leadership roles within companies and becoming more demanding clients for consultancies is leading to more thorough planning of consulting projects and selection of service providers: "We are seeing the beginnings of a shift in the competitive dynamics of consulting away from the primacy of integrated solution shops designed to handle all aspects of a client's engagement to modular providers that specialize in delivering a specific link in the value chain. As examples of such "modular solutions," Christensen cited emerging technology consultancies (Tata Consultancy Services, Infosys), market research experts (Gartner), database providers (IMS Health), and professional services firms (BTG). As a result of the disruption of the MC industry, Christensen saw four implications: consolidation (along with the death of some "losers"), the battle for SME business, the emergence of cross-boundary business models with technology aspects, and the steady invasion of hard analytics and technology (big data). Christensen concluded that "disruption of these businesses is undeniably underway" and "our long study of disruption has led us to one universal conclusion, which is that every industry will eventually face it".

11 years later, as this thesis is being written, we can see that the industry has indeed changed, although the dire predictions of Christensen and others have come true only slightly. All MBB firms (McKinsey, BCG, Bain) have grown in terms of revenue with CAGR of 6%, 13% and 12% respectively over 2014-2023 (Forbes, 2023c, 2023b, 2023a). Big4 firms (Deloitte, PwC,

EY, KPMG) also grew on average with 10% CAGR over 2013-2023 according to Kennedy Research reports. As mentioned in the introduction, it's hard to say how the overall MC market has changed in size since then, as different researchers estimate it quite differently, but according to some analysts like Kennedy Research, the market is still growing, albeit with a tiny growth rate of 1.3% over 2013-2022 (Businesswire, 2014; WSJ, 2023). Since 2013, MC companies have indeed adapted to the changing market realities and acquired many new competencies through M&A, mainly in the areas of data analytics, digital marketing, design, as well as specialized consulting firms. McKinsey & Company alone completed 12 acquisitions between 2013 and 2023 (Orbis database, 2024).

In recent article By Julian Birkinshaw and David Lancefield authors ask a question “How Professional Services² Firms Dodged Disruption?”. Birkinshaw and Lancefield define disruption as "an overturning of the established order, with incumbents losing out to new competitors. The authors drew on the work of Joshua Gans, who defined disruption as "what a firm faces when the choices that once drove a firm's success now become those that destroy its future" (Gans, 2016). Gans also previously proposed the framework, explaining that disruption occurs when incumbents fail to identify innovations in the products that customers demand (demand-side effect) or when incumbents fail to make the organizational changes necessary to compete with new entrants (supply-side effect) (Gans, 2016). Birkinshaw and Lancefield identify various demand-side and supply-side threats, as well as a combination of the two, that professional services firms have faced and describe how firms have addressed these challenges. The authors identify AI as the biggest supply-side threat that could eventually take over professional services activities. To date, many firms have already made significant efforts to build their own AI capabilities through partnerships and acquisitions. The biggest risk on the demand side is the unbundling of services that clients buy from a single provider, along with changing commercial arrangements that demand outcome-based deals. Incumbents are responding in two ways: first, by taking on only the most complex and challenging projects (high-risk, high reward); second, by spinning off some niche consulting activities to other firms; for example, Bain spun off The Bridgespan Group to focus on nonprofits. Birkinshaw and

² Professional services is a broad term that encompasses a wide range of services provided by experts in various fields, such as law, accounting, engineering, and IT. These services typically involve providing advice, expertise, or implementation of solutions to clients. So Management Consulting is subset of Professional services.

Lancefield note that AI could eventually affect both sides of the business, as some tech companies, such as Amazon, could use vast amounts of data to provide retail customers with the best predictions and recommendations. The authors also identified a few success factors that have helped professional services firms thrive: a constant effort to innovate for their clients, close collaboration between junior consultants and partners (unlike many traditional firms), and a cautious approach to investing in new activities. The researchers conclude that, so far, professional services firms have managed to avoid disruptions by successfully diagnosing the threat, tailoring their response to the challenges, and balancing their pragmatism with a healthy dose of paranoia (Birkinshaw & Lancefield, 2023).

By any definition, AI is a disruptive technology. Many great businessmen and pundits are betting that it will change humanity and especially the job market forever (including Bill Gates, Elon Musk, Yuval Harari, and many others). The question of how AI will affect MC in particular is still tiny but important, as big companies rely quite often on consultants.

2.3. Previous studies of GAI impact on management consulting

In this chapter, the author tries to capture the existing research that directly discusses the role of GAI in management consulting, and some aspects of management consulting work related to specific tasks that consultants perform and skills that they need to acquire. Some of the tasks consultants perform on a daily basis are more generic and exist in many other professional domains and contexts. Therefore, it's important not to limit the literature review of GAI's impact on the MC industry, but rather to look for some other contexts that might shed more light on the topic. For this reason, the author searched for articles on GAI applications in different domains such as academia and other types of white-collar jobs.

Before delving in analysis of literature around role of GAI in MC it's important to define what kind of skills and capabilities consultants demonstrate to perform their jobs. US Occupational Outlook handbook (OOH) defines 7 key tasks performed by management consultants: gather and organize information about the problems; conduct interviews; analyze financial and other data; develop solutions; recommend new systems, procedures, or organizational changes; make

recommendations through presentations or written reports; confer with managers to ensure changes are working (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2023). OOH also defines 5 important qualities of management consultants: analytical skills, communication skills (both writing and speaking), interpersonal skills, problem solving skills, and time management skills.

Speaking of academic literature, Kumar, Simon, and Kimberley identify a set of twenty-one strategic capabilities, categorized as functions, skills, and values, which are critical to success in management consulting. Among these, the three most critical functions highlighted are the quality of service, setting clear objectives, and problem-solving. Concurrently, the three paramount skills/values underscored are integrity and honesty, effective client-consultant communication, and credibility (Kumar et al., 2000). In other study authors identified consultants skills from the client's standpoint which include ability to listen and comprehend the client's needs, deliver high-quality service, maintain robust communication, exhibit integrity and honesty, and possess technical knowledge (Simon & Kumar, 2001). Jung in his 2010 study mentioned the importance of consultants for idea generation or problem recognition through dialogues with clients or workshops, which shape clients' imagination (Jung, 2010). It's necessary to highlight that consultants not only solve problems via thorough analysis but also play important role in nurturing client relationships, fostering a culture of knowledge sharing, encouraging innovation and proposing innovative solutions and ideas (Alvesson, 2012; Werr, 2012)

The important study on the impact of GAI in MC was conducted in 2023 by researchers from prestigious US universities in collaboration with the Boston Consulting Group and involved 7% of BCG headcount. This study provides empirical insights into the multifaceted effects of GAI on tasks performed by highly skilled consultants. For tasks classified as "inside the frontier," such as creative product innovation and development, writing tasks the use of Large Language Models (LLMs), specifically GPT-4, resulted in notable productivity enhancements (a 12.2% increase in task completion rate and a 25.1% increase in task completion speed) and a significant improvement in quality (over 40%). Conversely, for tasks "outside the frontier," where AI assistance was found to be ineffective or even detrimental, consultants using AI were 19 percentage points less likely to produce correct solutions compared to those not using AI. The task outside the frontier in the study involved complex business problem-solving that

required synthesizing quantitative data with interview insights. The findings (Dell'Acqua et al., 2023) underscore the importance for management consulting firms to identify tasks suitable for AI application and to equip professionals with the skills to effectively navigate this evolving technological landscape.

Some other recent papers converge on the idea that AI can contribute significantly to creative and innovation-oriented tasks ("inside the frontier"). For example, Girotra and colleagues find that LLMs can generate ideas faster and cheaper than humans, with higher average quality and variance in quality. In particular, in the context of idea generation for product innovation, LLMs outperform students from elite universities, generating a majority of the highest quality ideas (Girotra et al., 2023). The study by Jia, Luo, Fang, and Liao shows that AI assistance improves employees' ability to generate innovative solutions, especially for higher-skilled individuals, suggesting a skill-biased benefit of AI assistance in creative tasks (Jia et al., 2024). Writing skills, which also were considered as "inside the frontier" by Dell'Acqua et al., were proven to be significantly improved by assistance of ChatGPT 3.5 according to the experiment on business professionals, including consultants: the time taken to complete tasks decreased by 40%, and the quality of output increased by 18% (Noy & Zhang, 2023). What is also important, that Noy & Zhang study similarly to Dell'Acqua et al (2023) observed a decrease in inequality between workers; those with lower initial performance saw more significant benefits from using ChatGPT, suggesting that the technology might level the playing field among professionals.

Another important study by Cardon et al. shows high adoption of GAI among business practitioners³, with more than 80% using such tools. The most frequent use cases are research (49%), ideation (42%), drafting messages (42%), editing and revising messages (38%). There are slight changes between different levels of business practitioners, but the use cases are similar. Similar to Dell'Acqua's study, respondents still find little use for GAI in the areas of problem solving and data analysis. Study participants were also asked to identify the skills that are likely to be more or less important in the age of GAI. The most important skills for the future are "integrity", "strategic vision", "interpersonal skills", "innovation and creativity", which are very similar to the core consulting skills mentioned by (Alvesson, 2012; Kumar et al.,

³ Business school graduates, with technology, consulting, and financial services the most common industries

2000; Simon & Kumar, 2001; Werr, 2012). From these data we can infer that business practitioners predict significant improvements in LLM models' ability to analyze data, as both quantitative and qualitative analysis are mentioned as one of the less important skills in the AI age.

Speaking of the most frequent among business professionals use case of GAI application, data research or information retrieval, researchers tend to agree about upsides and downsides of GAI capabilities (Glickman & Zhang, 2024; Hersh, 2023; Huang & Huang, 2024). A key benefit is their ability to understand and refine queries, even when phrased ambiguously or with grammatical errors. Their conversational style allows users to refine questions iteratively, leading to increasingly accurate results. They also excel at summarizing long texts quickly and can handle specialized searches in fields like healthcare and law with greater precision. However, these strengths are tempered by notable limitations. On dark side of information retrieval, researchers emphasize the propensity of generative AI models to produce inaccurate or fabricated information, often referred to as "hallucinations," which can lead to misinformation in critical applications. The lack of appropriate citations further undermines the reliability of responses, as users cannot easily verify their accuracy. Professor of University of Washington Chirag Shah, specializing in search algorithms and recommendations systems eloquently points out that “The problem is that even when these systems are wrong only 10% of the time, you don’t know which 10%. People also don’t have the ability to quickly validate the systems’ responses” (Shah, 2023).

The research conducted in an academic setting observed the behaviors and outcomes of business students' use of GAI. The authors found that over-reliance on GAI diminishes students' critical skills in analyzing complex problems and evaluating different angles of the problem (Hyde et al., 2024). Similarly, Perera and Lankathilake suggest that unengaged interactions with GAI might light students' ability to hone their own analytical, reasoning skills and independent problem-solving abilities (Perera & Lankathilake, 2023). This is consistent with Dell'Acqua's concerns about AI capabilities: while in some areas the use of AI improves productivity and quality, in other areas the use of AI without scrutiny leads to poorer outcomes.

Researchers from OpenAI, OpenResearch, and the University of Pennsylvania performed data-driven analysis combining the capabilities of LLMs with job task requirements across various professions. They have similarly found that while the skill of "critical thinking" and "speaking" which are at the heart of management consulting jobs, is less likely to be impacted by LLM models but skills like "writing," "reading comprehension," and "active listening" are more likely to be augmented by GAI technologies (Eloundou et al., 2023). This suggests that management consultants who engage in data analysis, report writing, or developing presentations could experience significant efficiency gains with LLM integration. However, tasks that heavily rely on critical thinking and strategic decision-making—key aspects of consulting—may remain less affected by LLMs. These findings indicate that while LLMs can enhance certain facets of consulting work, the fundamental analytical and decision-making capabilities that consultants provide are likely to retain their value, underscoring the technology's role as a complement rather than a substitute in the consulting industry.

Another important area where consulting might learn from academia experience is assessment as MC generally considered as one of the most competitive sectors as according to some studies top consulting firms (Big3) invite only 10% of applicants to interview (coursera, 2023) and overall acceptance rate lies between 1-5% depending on the firm (managementconsulted.com, 2023; Oxford University Careers Service, 2024). While the recruitment process varies across the firm the steps, assessments beside screening and HR interview normally involve two distinct phases: tests for determining candidates general intelligence and cognitive abilities and series of case-interviews. Bain uses psychometric test to test candidates logical reasoning, numerical reasoning, verbal reasoning, and personality (Case Interview Hub, 2023). BCG currently uses online case chatbot "Casey" which has recently replaced previously used traditional multiple answers test similar to GMAT (myconsultingcoach.com, 2023). Similarly earlier McKinsey replaces its traditional famous pen-and-paper Problem Solving Test (PST) (Geerling et al., 2023; Oravec, 2023) with Problem Solving Game (PSG), which tests candidates' strategic planning and decision-making (McKinsey & Company, 2020). Another crucial element is case interview which established in consulting in 1990s and has become a golden standard for industry ever since (Asher & Lerner (Eds.), 1999). Cases where applicants solve business problems and provide imaginary clients with recommendations. serve dual purpose: it helps to identify

competent personnel and also symbolize the firm's commitment to rational, data-driven business problem-solving (Armbrüster, 2004). As ChatGPT-4 already demonstrated capabilities to achieve highest percentiles in most of kinds of tests and exams (OpenAI et al., 2024) and online assessments are becoming more and more common after COVID-19 for consulting firms. Hence, for consulting as well as for academia keeping integrity and preventing dishonesty is becoming challenging issue as GAI tools open avenues for new forms of cheating (Geerling et al., 2023; Oravec, 2023).

2.4. Research gap

The literature review conducted by the author focused exclusively on GAI technology, sidelining discussions around other AI and machine learning instances. The temporal scope was set between 2022 and 2024, coinciding with the period when GAI adoption saw notable traction, despite the existence of generative pre-trained transformers (GPTs) for a more extended duration. The review was restricted to academic journal papers, conference papers, and pre-prints or working papers, acknowledging the rapid emergence of new literature in this domain.

The author utilized several search engines, including Google Scholar, Scopus, and the WU Online Library Catalog Plus, employing a two-tiered search approach. The first tier aimed to directly identify articles discussing the use of GAI within management consulting. The second tier sought to uncover the indirect impacts of GAI on the skills and tasks pertinent to management consulting, as outlined in the preceding chapter.

The first tier of keywords used for the search was combination of “management consulting” OR “consulting” with “generative AI” or “generative artificial intelligence” or “Large Language Models” or “chatgpt” (as the most prominent instance of explored technology).

The second tier's keyword search paired generative AI-related terms with skills and qualities integral to management consulting: “information retrieval⁴”, “data analysis”, “communication skills”, “interpersonal skills”, “problem solving”, “critical thinking”, “time management”, “idea

⁴ Used as proxy to data collection and data search skills

generation”, “innovative solutions”. While not exhaustive, this skill set was deemed representative of crucial consultant competencies.

An additional "human intelligence" filter was applied to refine search results based on the name of the study or the abstracts. Author strived to eliminate articles with a primary focus outside the typical consultancy domain, such as computer science or healthcare, or those not aligning with management consulting routines based on the author's expertise. Notably, a substantial portion of the literature within the educational context was excluded unless it specifically addressed business school students. Besides, author excluded the articles if they were written in 2022 and 2023 but haven't received any citations.

To identify the research gap author observed a few key parameters across the found papers: whether GAI component directly discussed in paper, which skills were tested, whether the paper discusses the impact on MC industry and whether the paper discusses how they way consultants work would change. The result of literature table is depicted in Table 1.

Despite a thorough literature review, a discernible gap was identified. Only one paper by Dell'Acqua et al. directly focused on management consultants and how productivity changes for various types of tasks as well as draws conclusions about the impact of discoveries on way management consultants work. Four other papers were found that indirectly implied changes in the way consultants work by involving them in interviews, experiments, or surveys to explore task-specific impacts of GAI (Cardon, Fleischmann, Logemann, et al., 2023; Noy & Zhang, 2023; Rick et al., 2023; Ritala et al., 2024). The most researched skills are idea generation, creativity, writing, and critical thinking, while other important to consultants skills like problem-solving, data-analysis, interpersonal communication are far less researched. No papers were found which discuss the impact of GAI on MC industry or some of its important aspects like changes in organizational structure, value of management consulting for future clients, industry's risks, etc. This gap underscores an opportunity for in-depth research to explore how GAI is reshaping the management consulting landscape and the nuanced changes it brings to consultants' day-to-day tasks, as well as to look ahead and try to understand what the future of management consulting looks like in light of the ever-growing GAI technology.

Table 1. Literature table

#	Name	Key skills tested	Discusses GenAI component	Discusses changes in management consulting industry?	Discusses changes in management consulting way of working?	Research method
1	(Dell'Acqua et al., 2023)	Consultants' specific tasks: idea generation, writing, strategic analysis, idea generation, product innovation, data analysis, etc.	Yes	No	Yes	Experiment, interviews
2	(Cardon, Fleischmann, Logemann, et al., 2023)	Broad range of tasks of business professionals including research, idea generation, writing	Yes	No	Partly	Survey
3	(Jia et al., 2024)	Creativity and idea generation	Yes	No	No	Experiment, interviews
4	(Noy & Zhang, 2023)	Writing tasks	Yes	No	Partly	Experiment
5	(Hyde et al., 2024)	Critical thinking	Yes	No	No	Survey, field data
6	(Perera & Lankathilake, 2023)	Analytical skills and critical thinking	Yes	No	No	Interviews
7	(Eloundou et al., 2023)	Broad range of skills from writing and programming to critical thinking and science	Yes	No	No	combination of methods (data analysis, LLM testing)

8	(Lin, 2023)	Research efficiency, writing, data synthesis, critical thinking	Yes	No	No	Literature review, philosophical analysis, practical observation
9	(Zhai et al., 2024)	Problem-solving, critical thinking	Yes	No	No	Experiment, statistical analysis
10	(Chen et al., 2023)	Decision-making, risk management	Yes	No	No	Case study, empirical analysis
11	(Ritala et al., 2024)	Broad range of knowledge workers' skills	Yes	No	Partly	Interviews, inductive analysis
12	(Kanbach et al., 2023)	Business model innovation, content generation, critical thinking	Yes	N	No	Case study
13	(Holm et al., 2023)	Innovation process, organizational changes	Yes	No	No	Literature review, theoretical analysis
14	(Cardon, Fleischmann, Aritz, et al., 2023)	Writing in business communication, critical thinking	Yes	No	No	Survey
15	(Bilgram & Laarmann, 2023)	Innovation process, creative tasks	Yes	No	No	Experiment
16	(Nakavachara et al., 2024)	Data analysis, Writing	Yes	No	No	Experiment
17	(Yao et al., 2023)	Problem-solving in various domains	Yes	No	No	Experiment
18	(Rick et al., 2023)	Idea generation, problem solving	Yes	No	Partly	Experiment
19	(Essien et al., 2024)	Critical thinking	Yes	No	No	Survey, quasi-experiments

20	(Shaer et al., 2024)	Idea generation, idea evaluation	Yes	No	No	Experiment
21	(Evkaya & de Carvalho, 2024)	Data analysis	Yes	No	No	Experiment
22	(Hersh, 2023)	Information retrieval	Yes	No	No	Literature review
23	(Huang & Huang, 2024)	Information retrieval	Yes	No	No	Literature review, data analysis
24	(Glickman & Zhang, 2024)	Information retrieval, data synthesis	Yes	No	No	Literature review, data analysis
25	(Korinek, 2023)	Ideation, Writing, Background research, Coding, Data analysis, Math	Yes	No	No	Experiment

3. Methods

The method of conducting this study is qualitative using semi-structured interview as approach and collect data through one-to-one interviews. Collected data enables the author to build the gap between existing research and reality happening in management consulting industry.

3.1. Research questions

As the existing research was focused more on the specific tasks which are fully or partly automatized and supported by GAI and how productivity, quality of such tasks has changed current research doesn't have a goal to measure these topics in depth, but rather to contribute to the academic research by exploring previously untouched three areas, which became the research questions for the study:

- 1) How management consulting companies and their employees adapted to emerged and booming GAI technology?
- 2) What are the risks and benefits of using GAI for the MC industry, their clients, consultants working in MC?
- 3) How will GAI technology change MC industry in next 5-10 years?

The questionnaire for the semi-structured interviews was designed on the two levels: corporate and individual. For the first level, the goal was to understand how companies of various sizes and regions adapt their activities to recently emerged GAI technology. Author explored the following aspects of firms' adaptation: introducing policies and rules regarding using GAI tools; updating strategy and organizational structure; training employees; communicating with the clients and delivering the projects, and some other areas. On the individual level, questions were focused both status quo and future of management consulting. Questions asked were intended to reveal respondents' attitudes towards using new technologies in general and GAI in particular, explore use cases of gen. AI in daily consultant's duties, its pros and cons, productivity and quality gains. Moreover, respondents were asked to imagine the future of consulting in the next 5-10 years in the context of GAI and reason about the risks of the industry, personal job security, management consulting industry changes and evolution. As interview was semi-structured, some of the topics

could be skipped or some new added based on the flow of discussion and respondent's background (e.g. size of the firm they represent or level of seniority) but more or less the same structure of interview was followed for all the respondents.

3.2. Data collection and sample

The study targeted experienced management consultants who have understanding of the industry and familiar with GAI technology. In order to minimize biases of collected responses, author tried to diversify the sample of the interviewees and conduct interviews with consultants in different regions, company's types, and of different seniority. In total 21 interviews were conducted, each of which lasted between 25 – 58 minutes. All respondents for the interview were recruited through personal connections of the author.

All interviews except №9, 20 and 21 were conducted via Zoom and recorded using its feature. All participants gave their oral permission to record the interviews and opted-in for recording by using the appeared in Zoom button, when recording was started. With most of the respondents we agreed on interview being anonymous and not pointing out to exact company name but rather describing the company in more generic way like Big-3 firm, Tier-2 consulting firm, etc. Full list of the interviews can be found in Appendix,

It worth mentioning, that author managed to speak with representatives of all Big-3 (BCG, McKinsey & Company, Bain) and Big-4 firms (PwC, EY, Deloitte, KPMG), as well as some major Tier-2 consultancies like Roland Berger, AT Kearney, Arthur D. Little, Accenture, and some others.

Once interviews were conducted they were all transcribed with use of OpenAI speech to text tool Whisper (OpenAI, 2022). After automated transcription was ready, author conducted manual check of quality of transcription and edited some parts remembering the interview and re-listening some parts if needed. After transcription was ready, author manually sanitized the sensitive data like firm name, personal data, etc.

Due to the fact that most of author's respondents were native Russian speakers, the primary language for the majority of the interviews was Russian. In all these cases for analysis reasons interviews were translated into English with help of ChatGPT-4 and DeepL and author's manual editing afterwards to correct mistakes of LLMs. All manipulations namely creating transcript, validating its correctness, sanitization, and translation into English (if needed) were performed

by authors within 1-2 days after the interview was conducted in order not to forget important details of it.

The analysis of the interviews was conducting with the help of NVivo software, proprietary tool for organizing and analyzing qualitative data, as well as ChatGPT-4.

4. Data analysis and the results

4.1. Generative AI adoption in management consulting firms

In this chapter, author is examining various aspects of GAI adoption ranging from strategies, policies and rules to training, copyright issues, and new organizational roles.

Policies and regulatory frameworks for GAI

At the onset of ChatGPT's emergence in late 2022, approximately one-third of respondents indicated that their firms completely prohibited the use of ChatGPT until a better understanding could be achieved. The remaining two-thirds did not receive any specific instructions, hypothesizing that ChatGPT was merely another external tool and that consultants should always handle sensitive data with caution. As the manager of one global consultancy put it: *“we undergo extensive training on data management, especially how we handle data when given access to a client's data repositories. GNI hasn't changed our approach to data security; there hasn't been a need for additional measures or policies regarding its use⁵.”* These approaches marked the early stages of corporate attitudes toward GAI.

Later, somewhere in early to mid-2023, the rules adopted by consultancies regarding the use of GAI can be divided into two categories: formal policies and recommendations. Regardless of the form the policy takes, most companies strive to prevent consultants from uploading sensitive client or internal data to public GAI tools such as ChatGPT due to concerns about data leakage and maintaining client confidentiality. Two firms, one from the Big-4 and another the global consultancy, initially prohibited the use of these tools for any professional purposes. For

⁵ Here and further, quotes from respondents have been edited for clarity by removing filler words and sanitizing sensitive information. Additionally, the author's remarks to enhance understanding are included within brackets [].

example, a Big-4 firm blocked access to ChatGPT from the corporate network at the Middle East level a restriction that surprisingly still exists.

Some respondents noted that their firms distinguish between using client data in ChatGPT for educational or non-sensitive matters like research and other uses, though this is not always consistent. One respondent from a Big-4 firm highlighted the ambiguity of firm rules and its consequences: *“You can use it [GPT-4]. No one says you can, but no one prohibits it... Everyone knows that ChatGPT is being used, but no one talks to each other because they are afraid that someone will leak it or say that they didn't come up with the results themselves.”* Importantly, while most respondents are aware that some recommendations or policies on the use of GAI exist, they are unclear about the specifics and tend to rely on common sense, which varies widely. Some adhere to strict self-regulating rules like “I don’t enter any client’s data in ChatGPT,” while others believe it's acceptable to sanitize and then enter client data. To mitigate differences in self-regulation, one Big-3 firm has implemented strict protocols requiring employees to read and sign a consent form outlining how to use GAI tools responsibly, and only after that are they granted access to the firm's GAI tool.

These measures described by respondents illustrate how firms are striving to balance the benefits of GAI for enhancing productivity with the imperative to protect sensitive information. However, the effectiveness of these policies is challenged by the rapid pace of technological advancement, suggesting that data responsibility is becoming an increasingly individual concern. One interviewee from the global consultancy even argued that data responsibility has increasingly become an individual concern as technology develops faster than policies can be crafted by any company, rendering these policies superficial and general in nature. To avoid such self-regulation differences, one respondent shared that his [Big-3] firm has developed a matrix explaining what type of data can and can't be used even in the internal GAI tool, for example, health records or personal data cannot be entered to internal GAI.

Overall, respondents share the perception that firms cannot fully control potential data leaks in cases of usage public tools as ChatGPT by employees, especially juniors, and whether this data could be used by models for further training.

Selection of GAI tools

Interviews reveal a complex landscape of adoption, utilization, and perception across various firms. As shown in the Figure 1, most firms rely on OpenAI solutions in one way or another. Around one-third of respondents mentioned that companies use Microsoft's CoPilot, integrated into the Microsoft environment, as a corporate tool. While respondents were mostly unsure whether CoPilot is based on GPT-3.5 or GPT-4, most expressed the belief that it's likely the 3.5 version, as compared to the commercially available public ChatGPT-4. Another third mentioned that their companies implemented proprietary tools currently based on the GPT-3.5 version. The remaining third developed their proprietary tools, surpassing the functionality and user experience of GPT-3.5 and which is closer to GPT-4 "class". Mostly, the functionality of these proprietary GAI tools concerns the ability to interact with the internal knowledge base and gain insights based on past projects. Only a few firms are now looking forward to selling AI-enhanced tools externally or integrating them more deeply into strategic consulting services, indicating a forward-looking approach to leveraging AI for competitive advantage. For example, a Big3 firm has built and is piloting a tool that can create draft presentations or PowerPoint slides based on prompts and integrated into PowerPoint, while another global consultancy is trying to build a powerful market research and benchmarking tool that is currently being tested on projects but could eventually be sold externally to other firms.

Figure 1. Selection of GAI tools by respondent organizations (n=15 organizations)

Note: some companies use more than 1 tool

Table 2. Indexing knowledge databases with GAI tools (n = 15 organizations)

Firm type	Indexed internal knowledge base with GAI tool
Big 3	3 out 3
Big 4	0 out 4
Global consultancies	4 out 6
Small firms	N/A

Speaking of the number of tools used, most companies stick to one corporate tool; however, some (~30%) companies pursue a strategy of testing and developing several tools for different purposes. Usually, if a company has more than 1 tool, the distinction is simple: one tool is trained on external data, the second on internal data. Using more than 2 tools is an exception, but not unseen. An employee of a Big-3 company described that the company follows a "vendor agnostic" path and tries to avoid vendor lock-in, which means that the company tests many tools simultaneously and experiments which tools are better suited for different tasks. For example, they now use at least 3 tools in parallel: one is the corporate version of GPT-4, another can interact with the internal knowledge database, and the third tool is used to create presentations.

Another interesting aspect of tool selection is how consultants interact with publicly available tools that are superior to those officially implemented in their companies. Almost all respondents from companies that use CoPilot or other tools that are inferior to the publicly available GPT-4 said that they and their colleagues often use GPT-4 for professional tasks, even though this could pose a risk of data leakage. This is due to several drawbacks of internal tools: frequent factual errors, slow performance, and dependence on internal VPNs. On the other hand, GPT-4 offers additional functionality, such as analyzing PDF or text documents, producing more accurate results and providing a better user experience. Although using the public instance of ChatGPT-4 is associated with higher security risks, consultants rarely share such usage experiences openly, but feel that many others do as well.

There is also the issue of firm type. The analysis shows that small firms cannot afford to develop custom tools and lack sufficient intellectual capital and standardization to index their own knowledge bases. Respondents from small firms reported that management encourage consultants to use it and pay for the subscriptions. One respondent from small European consultancy shared that they to mitigate security risks by using open-source LLM models, which could be run on private machines for data-sensitive areas, e.g. analyzing client's documents or interviews.

Surprisingly, however, none of the Big-4 firms, which presumably have ample resources and have accumulated extensive intellectual capital from past projects worldwide, have attempted to train large language models (LLMs) on such data. Big-4 respondents expressed concern that

despite public announcements of significant investments in generative AI, the results of these investments are not yet visible or have not reached their regions, although respondents represented different regions: EU, UK, Middle East.

IP management with GAI tools

As GAI tools are officially used in most firms to varying extents, author explored whether consultants label their work as co-created with GAI in some instances. A common theme across almost all interviews is the absence of labeling when GAI tools like ChatGPT are used in creating client deliverables or proposals. Some consultants view such labeling as excessive, akin to citing “Google” as a co-creator, while others perceive it as an admission of inadequacy, potentially undermining the credibility of consultants. However, one manager from a global consultancy believes that it should be indicated, though she also sees this as an unlikely possibility in the next few years.

There were a few cases mentioned where the use of GAI was disclosed. One respondent described it as a “marketing gimmick” on some public reports, while a few respondents disclosed the use of GAI for images, citing DALLE or Midjourney models. Only one respondent shared that his firm [Big-3] discloses the use of GPT in footnotes, and this applies to both text and images in public reports.

An interviewee from a global consultancy highlighted a specific use case—issuing public documents such as whitepapers or reports for clients that might be used publicly. In such cases, the firm fears copyright infringement and plagiarism tools that catch generative AI, hence there is a direct ban on using GAI tools for such projects. A few other respondents talking about the same topic of issuing public papers or blogposts at their firms were not concerned about potential copyright issues yet.

Respondent 15: *“I’m going to say a dangerous thing now. I know that my supervisors periodically use it to write public articles. They gather three or four guys, throw out bullet points, the thoughts they want to be reflected. Then they have 40 bullet points and feed this into ChatGPT and it returns an article back to them, a set of paragraphs, so to speak, that takes into account everyone’s opinion and actually makes it all beautifully formatted. That is, they don’t*

outsource the thought process, but they do outsource, so to speak, the actual final story they wanted to tell.”

Training and skill development for GAI

Another area of research attention was the training provided by firms to consultants. Most respondents reported that firms provide training on GAI that is not mandatory. It's either webinars, classroom training, or just presentation materials that could be used to learn features of GAI tools and techniques for effective prompting.

A few companies actively engage employees to be "champions of technology". Such employees tend to be very interested in technology themselves, and therefore actively contribute to the company's efforts to train other, less technologically savvy colleagues. Such “champions” may have formal responsibilities to host weekly or monthly meetings where they try to answer other colleagues' questions in a Q&A format, or where “champions” share their own discoveries in interacting with LLMs. It's not just a way to engage employees in becoming familiar with GAI, as some participants also mentioned the existence of internal channels in Slack or other internal collaboration tools where curious about the technology consultants discuss the advancements, share use cases, ask puzzling questions, etc.

Another method of upskilling consultants in the GAI domain is to include the topic in a mandatory training program for every employee, including newcomers. Only three respondents shared that such approach exists in their firms; however, in several interviews consultants express that it could be very useful to have such approach and regret that their firms don't do it yet. Here are a few opinions on the matter.

Respondent 5: “At my previous firm there was this digital upskilling initiative. It was very structured, we had separate app, and it was mandatory for everyone. I think that was great and correct because I still appreciate those trainings; they were genuinely interesting. Now [with GAI] here wasn't a requirement that everyone must go through the training, take a test or anything like that. There were some trainings, but given that I, and likely others, were busy, I don't think there was super high attendance.”

Respondent 11 adds: *“I think it would be kind of bold if it was part of the mandatory training. We have a three-tier training system. One is a week-long training, once a year for everyone. The second is market-level training where the market decides. And the third is webinars and so on. All the webinars, people probably skip because they are working. But [GAI can be added] the week-long training or make a mandatory two-day training for all consultants on this topic [GAI] – that would be cool. But there's nothing like that. Maybe I'll propose it to my leadership.”*

Creation new roles and GAI business units

Among large firms, about two-thirds of respondents said their firms have either created new business units dedicated to AI or repurposed and expanded existing technology business units. These units are responsible for thought leadership in implementing AI for clients and internal AI projects, such as developing internal AI tools. A few respondents also reported that their companies had many GAI-related vacancies, but that these were mostly filled from within.

Not all respondents were aware of the existence of such units or roles in their organizations, as three out of four Big-4 employees shared uncertainty, as the company is huge, with hundreds of thousands of employees worldwide, and they may have just missed some announcements.

Interestingly, we also discussed whether some new jobs like "prompt engineers" would emerge as some common practices in consultancies, as for example Booz Allen Hamilton has tried in the US (Polpi, 2023). None of the respondents knew if prompt engineers are hired in their firms, neither as a new job nor as some replacement for interns, analysts, or researchers.

Formulating new strategies for GAI age

None of the interviewees were aware of GAI strategies per se in their organizations, while some interviewees hypothesize that such strategies are still in the works and could be realized soon. However, a few respondents from Big-3 firms and a technology-savvy global consulting firm described things that already look like strategic moves and bets in the direction of harnessing and exploiting GAI. One Big-3 firm has been conducting systematic internal projects since the rise of GAI to understand how GAI can be used for each business function and industry, in order to launch major "GAI transformations" that partially replace already classic "digital transformation"

projects. Another Big-3 company has sought to join several GAI partnerships with various tech firms like OpenAI, Anthropic, and is striving not only to consume products developed by technology companies, but also to actively participate in the development of new tools. Similarly, a global consulting firm deepened its longstanding partnership with Microsoft through their joint venture to accelerate the responsible adoption of AI among their clients.

Most of the companies for now follow a more reactive approach, trying to commercialize the growing demand from the customer side (described in the subchapter “Clients’ reactions to rise of GAI”).

Consultant perspectives on corporate adoption of GAI

Overall, the majority (~60%) of respondents expressed positive feelings about their companies' adoption actions to date. Notably, however, all respondents from the Big-4 companies expressed either neutral or negative feelings about the companies' actions due to the speed of developments and the slow diffusion of information and technology within large organizations.

Speaking of the adoption of GAI tools among consultants and the sentiments around them, every respondent author spoke with described the mood around GAI in their teams as rather positive, seeing them as tools that transform rather than replace their work. However, there are some interesting differences. First, in terms of age, younger employees tend to be more enthusiastic and proactive about using GAI tools, looking for new use cases and integrating tools into their workflow. For example, some young consultants described themselves as "cyborgs" or "prompt engineers" because they integrate GAI tools into a wide variety of daily tasks. Younger consultants even established a new paradigm, reports Respondent 8: *“If junior colleagues are setting tasks they ask “chatgpt this” instead of “google this”, it’s not coming from people above manager position.”* Meanwhile more senior consultants (managers and above) use GAI for a very limited number of cases (more about case studies in separate chapter). The second interesting aspect of GAI adoption concerns transparency and openness about its use among colleagues. While it is undisputed that GAI tools are employed across all companies, attitudes toward acknowledging their use vary significantly. In some organizations, there is an openness to admitting the use of GAI for idea generation and analysis results, whereas in others, there is a

palpable reluctance, with consultants preferring to keep such usage confidential. One manager (Respondent 15) complains that such questionable behavior by analysts can lead to confusing situations: *"I think there is a gray area here. We need some rules of the game, because otherwise, for example, I, as a project manager, get some results and sincerely believe, for example, that this person wrote it himself, did it himself, and so on, and I am going to present this result on one of the slides to the client."*

Clients' reactions to rise of GAI

When discussing the evolving nature of client engagement, two closely interconnected themes frequently emerged. The first concerns the low awareness among clients regarding how GAI technology works and how to harness it effectively—not merely to enhance their public image by stating "we use LLM models," but also to realize tangible financial benefits. Consequently, there is a growing number of requests from clients asking consultants to integrate or advise on GAI applications. Some respondents noted that clients are sometimes so eager to deploy GAI technology that consultants must explain when other technologies might be more appropriate for a specific use-case. Often, consultants themselves identify potentially valuable opportunities for GAI applications on the client's side and proactively propose such projects.

In addition to these primary themes, several other intriguing ideas emerged in discussions about client interactions. A few respondents argued that clients are demanding deeper insights from consultants, challenging them with the notion that results provided could easily be generated by ChatGPT; they seek more profound analysis. Another notable application of GAI by clients involves writing requests for proposals (RFPs). A few experienced consultants observed that RFPs now often include superfluous elements "clearly generated by ChatGPT," as the model tends to provide an exhaustive list of potentially relevant items that are not the focus of the project. As one respondent put it, *"If an RFP includes blatant nonsense, we prefer to discuss it directly with clients to correct it during the negotiation phase and clarify that detailed work on certain points doesn't make sense."*

One respondent from a Big-3 firm contemplated the implications of using GAI in project engagements and how billing might change if the workforce and time required to fulfill projects

were significantly reduced. He then proposed an intriguing idea that may become more common in the future: *"Imagine you have a big project, and then there's a project manager, and typically you have 5 or 6 people and consultants to deliver the project, and customers really feel it. You know, it's very impactful there on the ground with us here. But in the future, it could be just a project manager and an associate. How can you charge the same? I mean, this is really going to be like value selling. So, we do not charge by time. We're billing based on the value that we've created, and I think that's going to, you know, even reinforce the need for us to get into the value billing space, because customers want to see value and not like people on the ground, and at the end of the day, it doesn't really matter who delivered the project or who was there."*

4.2. GAI use-cases and value creation

Application of GAI tools by consultants

In all interviews, the researcher asked the respondents to share their instances of using GAI tools for consulting work. Respondents were not directly asked follow-up questions when they did a task with GAI, in case it didn't come to mind. The figure below shows the frequency of use cases across all 21 interviews.

Figure 2. How consultants use GAI today?

At the top of the list is research and information retrieval, as nearly all respondents use GAI for these purposes to some degree. The devil is in the details here, as this is not only the most common use case, but also the most controversial. The responses were quite similar across the

interviews, as respondents identified instances where GAI tools work well for their research and instances where they don't, details are in the Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of Good and Poor Fits for GAI in Research

Good fit	Poor fit
Foundational Research: Fit for initial exploration when little is known about the subject, providing a broad understanding of the basics.	Complex Research: Limited in assisting users to delve deeper into topics where they lack the necessary expertise to formulate advanced inquiries.
Niche research: Fit for exotic use-cases, especially in foreign languages like Arabic.	Sole Source Reliance: Problematic when GAI is used as the only research tool; while time-saving, it is usually insufficient.
Secondary Research: When one has a solid grasp of the topic and needs to refresh knowledge or delve deeper by asking the right questions.	No-Source Identification: When sources are not provided, it leads to challenges in validating information.
Ideation and Direction: Using GAI as a springboard to generate initial ideas and directions, paving the way for more traditional research methods.	Overreliance: When outputs are accepted uncritically, especially if results are shared with clients or applied without thorough verification.
Source Identification: When the tool cites its sources, enhancing the credibility and traceability of the information provided.	High-Risk: Inappropriate for crucial research components that decisively influence project outcomes due to reliability concerns.
Critical Evaluation: When GAI outputs are treated critically, recognizing potential inaccuracies by default and considering results as hypotheses rather than facts.	
Low-Risk: For research where findings are supplementary, such as data used in appendices.	
Foundational Research: Fit for initial exploration when little is known about the subject, providing a broad understanding of the basics.	

Some respondents also noted that they do not use the corporate tool or ChatGPT for research, but Perplexity.ai. Respondent 11 mentioned that *"In my universe, Perplexity, especially considering all the SEO queries, SEO results, has already beaten Google"*. While the table above describes common responses, there were some deviations from these practices. For example, one analyst mentioned that over time he learned how to perform even complex searches with reliable sources for benchmarking by experimenting with prompt strategies and using the "re-generate" button more often.

About half of the respondents indicated that they use GAI tools for a wide range of writing tasks, from routine emails to refining final deliverables. These tools are perceived to be very useful for a variety of writing tasks, with varying levels of complexity and formality. For routine communications such as emails and simple reports, GAI tools increase efficiency and accuracy. For more complex or high-stakes writing, such as client-facing documents or strategic proposals, GAI helps ensure that content is engaging and well-organized. And for non-native speakers or in

multilingual contexts, GAI greatly simplifies the challenge of writing fluently and appropriately in a second or third language. Speaking of writing tasks in general, users don't tend to differ much in the way they use GAI, although the intensity may vary: some report using GAI tools for every important communication, every word on the slide to polish the language, while others prefer to use it situationally, not trying to be "perfect" every time.

Another important aspect of consulting is brainstorming. Many respondents expressed appreciation for the quick and seamless "bounce-back" of ideas and view GAI tools as valuable brainstorming partners. These tools are particularly valued for their ability to quickly provide new perspectives and insights, which is critical at the beginning of a project when hypotheses are being generated. One respondent [Respondent 19] highlighted the practical benefits, stating, *"Sometimes it's very cool to battle hypotheses with it [ChatGPT-4]. You tell it situation and the problem, and it gives you something back. Then it's very interesting to test it against better information. It's a sort of expert replacement, I'd say. Then, with a good, more prepared list of hypotheses, you can go to the experts."*

Approximately 40% of respondents benefit from GAI's ability to summarize, synthesize, or extract information from large documents, such as customer responses to data requests or external reports. However, many respondents are unable to take full advantage of this capability due to corporate restrictions on GAI tools and rely on their private instances of ChatGPT-4 for non-sensitive data.

Interestingly, data analysis tasks, probably the most prevalent in the consulting profession, don't involve GAI tools and these capabilities are rarely mentioned by respondents. Even though some special plugins appear in the public instance of ChatGPT-4, such as the DataAnalyst plugin, which allows analyzing spreadsheets, consultants don't use them either for security reasons or simply because they are not yet familiar with these tools and analyze data as in pre-GAI times. Other use cases mentioned by respondents were less common but nevertheless demonstrated the versatility of GAI applications when consultants experimented with them to create unique use-cases, occasionally saving significant time. These varied applications ranged from developing custom GAI bots based on open-source models tailored to specific needs, to analyzing video conferences and assisting with feedback for team members during projects. Generally speaking,

it was noted that the performance of GAI tools met users' expectations; thus, the scope of application depends on the users' familiarity with the technology, the time they invest in interacting with it, and their success in identifying useful cases for their specific needs.

Perceived value of GAI tools in management consulting

The author discussed with most of the respondents the perception of improved productivity and quality of consulting projects through GAI tools. In terms of productivity, the majority of respondents perceived only small changes (less than 10%) in their productivity, as the proportion of tasks they perform that could be optimized with GAI is quite small. This is strongly related to their current position in the company, as all respondents who noticed small changes are managers and above, and therefore do less research and analysis work themselves, often delegating it to junior colleagues. One respondent [Respondent 4] also noted that the perception of productivity might be misleading because using the GAI tool saves time that wouldn't be spent without it: *“It's hard to even say that I saved two hours; I would not have spent those two hours. I would have just done a worse job. I spent the same amount of time in the end. It's just that this efficiency went into the output, not my saved time.”*

Younger employees who hold analyst-level positions and whose work relies heavily on insight generation, research, and data analysis see a more significant impact on their productivity, ranging from 20% to 200%. Some of them compared their work hours before GAI tools were available and today and reported that they work much less while producing similar levels of insights.

Speaking of GAI's impact on quality, most respondents either shared the feeling of uncertainty about how to compare it or didn't notice any impact on quality, as their firms hold standards of deliverables at the highest level regardless of the tools used. Senior executives (partner level) are responsible for reading and accepting final versions before sharing with clients, and this hasn't changed with the availability of new tools. However, one Big-4 manager [Respondent 1] noticed that quality overall improves: *“Even if the same consultants who made the report lacked knowledge, they still made it. In general, the documents became much better than without using*

it [GAI tool]. Even if there are some gaps in the content, at least it's not embarrassing to send the document to the client because it will be written in good language. That's good.”

4.3. Future of management consulting

In this section, the author presents the respondents' reflections and their visions for the future of consulting in light of GAI development. We discussed potential risks, changes at the industry level, organizational and skills changes, and areas of automation. During the interviews, respondents were asked to imagine the short to medium-term future, over the next 5-10 years, to answer the questions.

Future roles for humans in consulting

Starting from the topic of automation areas, all respondents described the potential for automation in analyst-level work. Many consultants discussed junior position tasks across three major areas: (1) data discovery and research; (2) data analysis and synthesis; (3) building presentations and recommendations.

Regarding the first area, there appeared to be a consensus around research tasks, as current GAI tools already possess quite impressive capabilities; hence, respondents see how this could be further improved. A few areas of concern about research automation by GAI tools include the necessity to verify research results by humans and access to proprietary databases, which might not be granted to them.

Data analysis and synthesis appeared to be a less evident area for automation according to the respondents. While the majority expressed opinions that it's very likely GAI could automate typical analytical tasks performed by humans today, others only foresee some very basic analysis being automated or hardly see how data analysis might be automated at all.

Respondent 15: *“When we talk about status quo analysis, GAI could help with what we do in the first couple of weeks during the projects. If we talk about the target picture, the strategy, I think no matter how good the technologies are, they will not replace it because the level of interrelationships in a target picture is very complex, very difficult to structure and automate. I*

do not believe in the possibility that any technology, including GAI, would advise me on how to build or determine pricing at a given moment, in my place X, in territory Y, for customer Z.”

Respondent 17: *“Now ChatGPT makes mistakes in very simple calculations, one-line logic. I think that's the most problematic area. Business and financial models we build sometimes require complex logic and they should be easily verified by managers and clients. So, I don't see how data analysis could be automated soon.”*

Speaking of arguably the most important and visible to clients part of consulting work, presentation slides, most of the consultants either didn't mention it in automated areas of work by GAI or expressed doubts that it's possible any time soon. Only a handful of consultants who either have experience using such tools at their firms already or are more technologically savvy and understand the underlying principles of GAI better, shared that slide creation isn't a big problem for GAI tools to automate.

Respondent 4: *“I've already played around; they [GAI tools] can make slides. You just need resources, and they will make decent consulting slides. Give them a good database, train them well, give them access to client data. Here you go, a ready-made consultant, online 24/7.”*

Overall, despite high tendency to believe in rising automation in junior consultants tasks, around half of the respondents directly mentioned that automation doesn't mean complete automation or full replacement of junior positions but rather sort of the blend of machine and human work, symbiotic relationships between GAI and consultants, who need to use these tools like everyone uses today Excel or PowerPoint, be able to validate information and have ownership over the conducted research or analysis.

Among the areas of consulting work that are hard to automate, respondents, albeit in different words, also described three areas: (1) various aspects of human interactions, (2) strategic thinking, and (3) supervision and management. These areas and responsibilities of consulting jobs respondents associated with roles of Manager / Project Leader and above, up to Partner.

Starting with the most doubted area of automation, human interactions, none of the participants foresee any changes on this surface coming from GAI development. The domains like

conducting meetings with clients, conducting interviews to gather information, communicating ideas between team members and to the clients, selling the project are intrinsically humane and can't be replaced by a machine anyhow, according to respondents. *"The only thing I can imagine are some fantastical scenarios where they create a robot in human form that could replace consultants, but practically I doubt it."*, shares Respondent 7 not without a laugh. Some respondents see such a barrier not only as limiting the power of technology but also as an essential part of the consulting business. Respondent 1 points out that the value of a consulting project for clients is often beyond the scope of work: *"Clients want to have interesting conversations with consultants. It's kind of meaningful leisure for them. In general, client executives communicate with consultants primarily to develop their own horizons and subconsciously find ideas to solve the tasks that formally underlie a particular project. In this context, clients will still perceive the main point of contact as people with rich experience, senior level."* Another consultant from a Big-3 firm [Respondent 20] recognizes another interesting aspect of consulting jobs directly linked to the human level – credibility: *"GAI won't replace consulting because of human aspect. It matters as there are always exceptions and different business goals. For example, not always companies seek to maximize profits in particular time; sometimes they make strategic moves that might maximize their profits in the long run but not in short term. I doubt that GAI can help clients with such issues. Credibility comes not from a consultant or analyst but from a Partner. Partner has credibility and trusted relationships with clients"*. He continues, *"Credibility in consulting matters most. CEOs often don't know what to do, or they know what to do but they want consultants to validate and improve these ideas, and in case it doesn't work, they have someone to blame. So, consulting won't disappear as tech firms don't have this credibility yet."* Similarly, another Big-3 firm consultant [Respondent 10] explains that consulting is not only about finding the right answers and conducting great analysis for clients: *"We are in a people's business. You can, of course, say: "Hey, we are super great at crunching numbers, doing excel spreadsheets. Nice presentations. Let's say all of this is automated." And you know, clients hire us, they send us the data. We put it all in GPT-7 and they get the final deliverable back in one day comparing with what we did in 6 months before. But how impactful will it be? It won't be impactful because we need to work with the client on the problems, we need to understand the problems. Again, it's a people's business. And we need to be close with the clients and take them on the journey."*

"Thinking" or "strategic thinking" was mentioned in the answers of a few respondents in a way that humans would still be in charge of structuring the problems, critically assessing how to tackle them from various angles, as GAI tools won't be able to provide the infamous in consulting "so what" aspect, according to Respondent 6.

Some respondents also see increasing value in supervision and control not only over the teams but also over the GAI tools which are more and more integrating into everyday workflows. Not only analyst-level positions would be encountered with mastering emerging tools, but managers too. Managers have to utilize them to automate easy administrative tasks but pay more attention to the sanity check and validation of the team's work.

Organizational Changes in Consulting Firms

Following the discussion in the previous chapter about the automation perspectives of certain consulting tasks, respondents speculated on the future roles of consultants, particularly those at the junior level. Most agreed that these positions would be significantly impacted, though there was some disagreement about the specifics.

About 40% of the respondents mentioned that fewer consultants would be needed as many of their current tasks could be substantially reduced, thereby affecting team sizes: tasks that yesterday required four analysts might tomorrow be accomplished by only two. This potential reduction in analyst-level positions could transform the "classic consulting pyramid," where the base is made up of the largest number of junior consultants, and fewer are needed as you move higher up. A few managers highlighted an interesting paradox that might arise in such a scenario: if fewer consultants are needed but the number of managers remains the same, how will these managers be adequately trained? However, one Principal of a global consultancy [Respondent 7] does not see this as a major issue: *"Managers will come from the business world with the necessary skill set. Not everyone grows from an analyst or intern to a project manager. There are great reverse cases, so I don't see a problem here."*

Not all respondents share this pessimistic view about the number of junior consultants needed. Four respondents believe that the number of analysts will remain roughly the same, but the

nature of their jobs will change. They also see ongoing layoffs in consultancies as unrelated to automation but rather tied to economic cycles. One respondent [Respondent 4] eloquently described the potential alternatives for the inevitable increased productivity of consultancies and expressed his doubts about massive personnel layoffs: *“With GAI tools you get just a massive increase in efficiency. Then the question is where you direct it. First option: you can work 3 days a week for 6 hours and do the same amount of work. The second, you'll need 5 times fewer people, and you'll just keep the smartest ones, so to speak. Third, you'll keep the whole team, everyone will work the same, and you'll just earn crazy amounts of money. There are different directions to channel this efficiency, and it doesn't necessarily all go into staff reduction. I think it probably won't be like that.”*

Approximately half of the respondents noted that the nature of the analyst-level job would be transformed to some extent. A few junior respondents provided quite radical views about such changes: *“the analyst role would shift to writing prompts and making correct conclusions from them”* or *“perhaps a chip will appear, and analysts would generate some thoughts that immediately appear on the screen for further analysis.”* Others emphasized that today's analysts would just perform the work of senior analysts or even managers at times, as they would be more involved in structuring, defining problems, and data verification, rather than performing routine tasks like drafting a slide or conducting lengthy research due to GAI support.

Transformative trends in management consulting

Following the discussion at the organizational level, participants also described their perspectives on how the industry might change due to the development of GAI. Starting on an optimistic note, none of the participants believed that GAI would “kill consulting” in the next 5-10 years at least. The most commonly observed sentiment was an increase in productivity, which is quite straightforward given that respondents already perceive some effect on productivity today and expect this to only grow.

Another area of change, noted by about a third of the participants, was the scope of work. Some respondents believed that simple data crunching projects, which are usually only parts of larger projects, could be performed by clients themselves. Additionally, the phases where consultants

try to understand a client's business could be eliminated or radically reduced, as GAI could support this phase and provide consultants with a comprehensive and structured view of the client's business without any direct involvement from consultants. Furthermore, consultants expect an increase in projects related to the implementation of AI and GAI technologies, similar to digital transformations. One senior analyst noted that the demand for "general consulting" might be reduced as ChatGPT-like models help clients find answers themselves; however, specific projects, like transforming operational models where deep competence, industry knowledge, and experience are required, would be in high demand, as public GAI tools won't have access to such knowledge.

A Project Manager from a Big-3 firm [Respondent 19] suggested another possible shift in consulting scope – back to the roots: *"I think the focus will likely shift to what consulting was supposed to be about initially. Now consulting turned into just drawing thousands of slides for 80 hours per week. Initially, the idea was that clients come in and say, 'You guys are smart, come up with something interesting that I couldn't think of on my own.' I believe it should return to something like that."*

Opinions varied regarding which consulting firms would benefit or lose from the rise of GAI. On the one hand, respondents noted that large companies have obvious advantages in training their models on a large corpus of proprietary data, making them more efficient and competitive - advantages that small consultancies cannot afford. One respondent from a Big-3 firm also pointed out that "generic consulting" is already becoming very cheap as it could be done by anyone, and this trend would only accelerate; hence, the rise of GAI would be a filter for true strategy consultants: *"[In the future] If you don't go into super precise, super clear things, but just do this kind of descriptive consulting like 'I'll sing about this and I have that in my repertoire also' - I think this type of consulting will be cut off completely."*

On the other hand, some respondents recognized the advantages of smaller firms due to their higher flexibility, ability to hire and build new competences quickly, and access to knowledge and information which democratizes, giving new firms an edge over legacy ones.

A few respondents also recognized a growing demand for consulting as it becomes more accessible, especially to SMEs who couldn't afford any consulting before. *"There would be a niche for rough, unpolished templates for SMEs because currently, they can't afford full consulting services. So, it would be an accessible, inexpensive but still strategic consulting service,"* shares Respondent 7.

Regarding the risks for the consulting industry, respondents generally named just a few like privacy and security, copyright issues, and over-reliance on GAI by consultants; however, they tend not to exaggerate the probability of these risks having a big impact on MC. A Big-3 consultant also noted that there is a risk for companies to not build GAI capabilities in time and become obsolete and outcompeted by other players; therefore, many consultancies try to invest in this area and even run loss-making projects just to get early credentials. Finally, only one consultant [Respondent 4], speaking about the risks to the industry, foresees major risks to the industry and, ironically, hopes that consulting will change dramatically to adapt to the GAI age.: *"I hope that risks for the industry will emerge and become more profound. I really hope so. Because sometimes you read some work [of consultants], and you think it would have been better to just burn that money in a stove. At least someone would have warmed up instead of spending it on you. Because sometimes it's just [nonsense]"*.

Implications on personal job security

Near the end of the interviews, the author asked the consultants to describe how they felt about their personal job security in consulting given the emergence of GAI. None of the respondents expressed any fear that GAI would take their jobs.

The reasons for this could be grouped into 4 different categories, as shown in Figure 3. The first

reason respondents mentioned is that they would just use GAI and improve their productivity, so there is no risk for them, but they recognize that consultants who don't adapt to the technology will face job security risks. This sentiment is shared by both junior and senior consultants.

Respondent 4 formulated it a following way: *"I think consultants who want, will benefit from it*

Figure 3. Why GAI won't take my job?

[GAI]. It's like the internet. Most likely, smart people will become smarter, and stupid people will become stupider. Another magnifying glass, in my view."

The next area of hope for consultants is interpersonal communication, client interaction and project management. Respondents, regardless of their current position, believe that while GAI will get better over the next 5-10 years, they have either already shifted or will shift their job responsibilities from routine analysis and data collection to areas that are safer from GAI intervention. Two consultants expressed the strong belief that consultants like themselves are better off than almost any other white-collar worker because they have broad knowledge and unique skills to synthesize information from many different sources to support decision making. These skills are becoming even more valuable as technology evolves and the complexity and volume of information on the client-side increases.

Respondent 2: *"I don't believe my skills are outdated or that there's a need for new technologies in the projects I'm working on. Consulting, to me, is about providing analytical skills and decision-making support that clients can't find internally. Even though AI might assist with some aspects of analytics, decision-making involves factors beyond what's available online or computationally. Clients need consultants to gather and synthesize information from various sources to help make informed decisions. I don't see Generative AI replacing these core aspects of consulting anytime soon."*

A couple of consultants tend to believe that they are in demand simply because they can support the implementation of AI/GAI technologies on the client side. Similar to digital transformation, such projects would require consultants who have had similar experience in the past.

Interestingly, only 3 out of 21 consultants agreed that they shouldn't be complacent about their job security and should keep in touch with technology development, because everything is changing very quickly, and they may need to learn new skills to adapt to this pace.

The viability of discontinuing GAI usage

Finally, a discussion on the future of consulting ended with a provocative question: Can consultancies stop using GAI due to various risks? Undoubtedly, the consensus was that it's very

unlikely. Some argue that banning GAI is like shooting oneself in the foot: it immediately makes the firm less competitive, as dozens of other firms will emerge if some incumbents stop using GAI. Therefore, consultancies would not only allow the use of GAI, but encourage consultants to use it in order to remain competitive on price and quality with other companies. Another key reason why the proliferation of GAI tools seems impossible to stop could easily be described by another metaphor close to the respondents' answers: "You can't put the toothpaste back in the tube". In other words, it is impossible to stop the progress, and even if companies officially ban the technology, people will still use their private products as ChatGPT if they see benefit from it, which would be even more dangerous from the companies' perspective. The only reason why GAI could be banned, mentioned by a few respondents, is a massive data leak. Respondent 11 shares: *"Consultants are very protective of their data. If there are more models, consultants will work with larger ones; there could be leaks, and then it would be explained that BCG works with such and such a pharmaceutical company, McKinsey with such and such a military company... That would be a disaster. I don't know how seriously they [management] take that risk now."* However, such cases could happen and without GAI, consultants use tons of other cloud products from Microsoft and Google, rely on them to write sensitive business emails, make presentations, store databases, etc. A Big3 manager [Respondent 19] explains: *"I can imagine some data or some deliverables leaking out. There could be some reputational issues for us, of course, but it would probably be more of a hit to OpenAI than to us. I think we would prove that the leak wasn't our fault."*

5. Discussion

This chapter would describe how the research gap was filled with respect to 3 broad questions: (1) GAI adoption in MC, (2) the risks and benefits of consultants' use of GAI for the industry, the consultants themselves, and their clients; and finally, (3) the future of management consulting in light of the technology. In addition to addressing the research gap, this chapter would highlight how personal experiences and use cases of consultants using GAI tools align with existing research touching on common business tasks.

Starting with the first part of the research gap, GAI adoption in consulting firms, research has shown that adaptation to GAI tools is not evenly distributed among consulting firms. According to recent article of Cook, Hagi, and Wright (2024), companies can integrate GAI at three ascending levels of sophistication to gain competitive advantages. The first level involves adopting available GAI tools (e.g. ChatGPT) to enhance operational efficiency across various organizational functions. Progressing to the second level, firms customize GAI solutions utilizing their proprietary data, thereby enriching customer interactions and product personalization. The third level, entails developing advanced AI systems that engage in continuous learning through automatic data feedback loops from user interactions, fostering a dynamic, self-enhancing AI ecosystem that delivers tailored customer experiences and drives competitive differentiation. Using this classification, majority of the firms are still at the first level of GAI adoption, as they simply use tools off the shelf, sometimes slightly customized, acting like “AI takers” (Jacobides et al., 2021). A minority of firms are attempting to build GAI tools internally using proprietary data, thus qualifying as 2nd level GAI adoption. None of the companies have yet demonstrated 3rd level capabilities, according to the author's observations of respondents' responses.

To some extent, the research also highlights that consultancies (especially Big-4 firms but not only) are not that different from their clients in terms of AI adoption: their inherent business complexity and legacy requires significant efforts to redesign the organizational processes around new AI technologies (Tambe et al., 2019). Difficulties of adoption also lie down in current capabilities of firms to leverage data to optimize business processes. In particular, the firms which have issues with standardization of business processes between offices or not yet

obtain well-structured knowledge management systems accurately representing experiences of past projects, can benefit far less from GAI deployment which is not different from implementation of other AI tools (Brock & Von Wangenheim, 2019). It is interesting to note that all consultancies have already responded at least to some extent to the increasing demand from their clients, offering them services on how to improve their business with GAI, publishing white papers on the subject in the hope of establishing themselves as technology experts, while internally in many of these consultancies there have been little, or no changes related to GAI. This situation might remind of famous proverb “the cobbler's children have no shoes”. Consultancies are proficient in change management project for their clients. GAI requires them to conduct huge change management internally.

Regarding the second part of the research gap, the risks and benefits of GAI for management consulting, the consultants surveyed remain overwhelmingly positive about the current state of the industry and the positive effects of GAI. Among moderate risks some consultants mentioned: privacy and security, copyright issues, and over-reliance on GAI leading to worse decision making. These risks have been well-documented in recent literature, reflecting a growing awareness of the potential risks GAI poses. Privacy and security risks, as highlighted by (Humphreys et al., 2024), are particularly acute, given the speed at which firms adopt GAI without adequate safeguards, which can lead to severe cyber vulnerabilities. Furthermore, the rapid implementation and integration of these technologies often outpace the establishment of necessary ethical guidelines and risk management practices (Humphreys et al., 2024; Renieris et al., 2024). In realm of copyright risks, (Verma, 2023) distinguishes two potential sides of the problem: on one hand, employees might use proprietary information in the prompts, leading to input copyright infringement. On the other hand, the output from generative AI tools might contain copyrighted information, which could be used by consultants in client reports or public documents, leading to output copyright infringement. Clearly, legal voids or ambiguities related to copyright with respect to GAI in different jurisdictions complicate the mitigation of this risk (Thongmeensuk, 2024). To conclude the discussion on MC industry risks, mentioned risk of over-reliance and over-trust in GAI could affect decision making (Humphreys et al., 2024) and a "human in the loop" is needed to mitigate this risk to some extent. (Baxter & Schlesinger, 2023; Gosline, 2024).

When discussing personal job security, consultants expressed an overall sense of optimism. Less than 15% of respondents voiced concerns about their future job prospects, which is significantly lower than in another study that surveyed a broader range of business professionals, where nearly 30% of respondents indicated such concerns (Cardon, Fleischmann, Logemann, et al., 2023). A primary reason for this confidence is the complementary nature of GAI to their existing skill sets of consultants. They believe that GAI tools will continue to improve their efficiency and productivity in certain tasks without completely replacing their roles, which is consistent with existing research that foresees GAI's role in automating some tasks rather than jobs. In the interviews conducted, junior consultants demonstrated noticeable enthusiasm and a proactive stance towards the integration of Generative AI tools into their workflows. Some of them described their role using vivid metaphors such as 'cyborgs' or 'prompt engineers,' which underscore a symbiotic relationship between their consulting acumen and AI capabilities. This observation aligns well with the findings of (Dell'Acqua et al., 2023) who noted similar trends in technological adoption among early-career professionals. However, it's important to clarify that while younger consultants showed more overt enthusiasm for exploring new use cases of GAI, the use of these tools is not confined to them alone. The age of the consultants interviewed ranged from the early 20s to late 40s; therefore, none were in the traditionally 'senior' age group of 65+. Moreover, surveyed consultants in senior roles, including those at principal and partner levels, were also regular users of GAI tools, suggesting that the adoption of new technologies transcends age and is more linked to professional roles and the perceived value of the technology in enhancing consulting practices.

In addition, when discussing job security and the impact of GAI on management consulting as a profession, consultants emphasized the importance of soft skills such as critical thinking, decision-making, and client engagement, in addition to more technical aspects such as data analysis, research, and presentation development. This holistic skill set is considered crucial to consulting and unlikely to be entirely replicated by GAI. While many consultants acknowledged potential risks for junior positions that are more involved in technical tasks, they generally felt secure due to their current seniority or anticipated career growth. They foresee themselves transitioning towards roles that focus on strategic thinking, client interaction, and other uniquely human aspects of consulting that are less susceptible to automation. This confidence is consistent

with previous research emphasizing that strategic and critical thinking, as well as interpersonal tasks, remain firmly within the domain of human expertise (Eloundou et al., 2023).

The third part of the research gap, the future of management consulting, could be described as optimistic, as none of the consultants surveyed see disruption coming, and most expect productivity gains from GAI, as well as some organic shifts in the scope of work and types of engagements with clients. GAI is here to stay. Consultants unequivocally agreed to that statement during the interviews as they see value in the technology as well thousands of their colleagues worldwide. The question remains as to how consulting as a business and consultants as individual contributors will continue to adapt to the changes brought about by GAI. This part will be discussed in more detail in the next chapter “Practical implications”.

To conclude the discussion section, let's reflect on the use cases of GAI in MC. The results of the research are consistent with the previous study (Cardon, Fleischmann, Logemann, et al., 2023) as research, ideation, writing tasks, and summarizing texts top the list in both cases; however, it seems that the intensity of using GAI tools for information retrieval (data research) is higher in consulting than for business professionals in general, as 95% of respondents reported using GAI for this purpose, compared to 50% in the Cardon et al. study. Insights into use cases also revealed an interesting pattern: the performance of GAI tools met users' expectations; thus, the scope of application depends on users' familiarity with the technology, the time users invest in interacting with it, and their success in identifying useful cases for their specific needs. A similar point was also made by Jeremy Utley, Professor at Stanford, the world's leading expert on creativity and innovation (Strategy skills, n.d.)

6. Practical implications

Going back to Christensen and his book Innovation Dilemma, he argued that disruption occurs when the performance of technology exceeds the needs of customers. And when that happens, the basis of competition changes. The basis of competition in consulting is already changing because of the use of GAI by consultants and the value it adds to their productivity. GAI might not kill consulting, but it might kill some firms and individuals not willing to adopt to new reality. For that consultants and incumbent firms need to harness GAI themselves to be able to

provide better advice to their clients. It might change traditional consulting business on many aspects and poses a few difficult questions to the industry:

- How to ensure ethical and responsible use of GAI?
- Which skills are expected from consultants and how to teach them properly?
- How to change performance evaluation practices?
- How increasing productivity will change consulting value proposition?
- How would project workflow change?

This list is not exhaustive but offers a glimpse into the myriad of potential challenges that may soon emerge, as observed during the interviews. While this section does not claim to provide definitive answers to these complex questions, it aims to offer some directions for future action based on the findings of this research and author's reflections.

How to ensure ethical and responsible use of GAI?

According to a recent international panel, the majority of AI experts believe that companies around the world are not sufficiently building their risk management capabilities to address AI-related risks (Renieris et al., 2024). This research also implicitly shows that some consultancies have not yet decided how to address the ethical and responsible use of AI or how to disseminate this knowledge among consultants. It seems important for all consultancies to establish clear risk management procedures, policies or charters to help employees navigate emerging ambiguities. Consultants should not feel embarrassed about using GAI and must be transparent about it with their supervisors. Currently, the approach to using GAI often depends on a manager's personal stance on technology. If the supervisor is technologically averse, consultants might feel compelled to conceal their use of GAI as if it were illicit. Consultants want to deliver value to their clients, and clients want to get the best advice based on the best technologies available. Hiding the use of generative AI might be as absurd as a radiologist saying, "Don't worry, only humans will look at your scan. AI won't be used." If AI is the best technology today, why not use it?

However, transparency is important and consultants may need to disclose their use of GAI both internally and to their clients. This practice seems to be neglected so far as consultants perceive GAI tools akin to Google "*We don't cite Google, right?*", mentioned one respondent. But clients

might have opposite opinion. Research by Source Global published in December 2023 indicated that 35 percent of clients want firms to be open about which parts of a report were produced by AI, and 43 percent expressed concerns over data protection and privacy related to AI-generated work. Only some consultancies are cautious and avoid using GAI in public reports until these issues are properly regulated, while others use it extensively without disclosure. On one hand, lack of transparency could undermine the trust. On other hand, transparency about using GAI might create doubt among clients regarding the consultants' ability to provide advice independently of these systems.

Certain legal vacuums and the lack of AI risk management frameworks do not help to address such difficult issues. While AI risk management practices and ethical and responsible use of AI are still evolving, it's clear that consulting firms need to make thoughtful decisions that weigh the pros and cons for their business.

Which skills are expected from consultants and how to teach them properly?

Consulting firms need to recognize that the new reality of consulting comes with generative AI, which requires not only maintaining traditional consulting skills, but also developing a new set of skills. In consulting, learning often occurs on the job. Nevertheless, various trainings in other crucial domains existed in consultancies. Starting from basic research, critical thinking, PowerPoint skills, and Excel modelling to more advance technological tools like PowerBI, Alteryx, Tableau, and others. GAI tools should now be added to this list, requiring consultants to understand these tools not merely at a layman's level but deeply enough to fully harness and utilize them. In addition, the current way of doing things, such as verifying research results, could be indirectly affected by GAI. Some firms offer voluntary training, a few have made it mandatory, but many still have no training at all. According to recent article (Tamayo et al., 2023), leading organizations recognize reskilling as a strategic imperative that is critical for maintaining competitive advantage in rapidly evolving fields such as AI. Consultancies shall take GAI disruption seriously and need to identify new skills that will be required in the near future, ensuring these are clearly defined and aligned with the strategic goals. This foresight will allow the creation of targeted training programs that are not merely elective but are essential

components of a consultant’s development path, critical for their future competitiveness. It’s also important that re-skilling initiatives go beyond classroom and integrates directly into the daily workflow. Consultancies shall not forget also to cheer champions of the technology, helping them to spread their knowledge across the firm, so peers learning from their peers, which now used only by handful of firms.

Whatever approach is taken, MC firms might need to re-evaluate their training and development strategies soon to ensure that these are not only proactive but also adaptive, equipping their workforce to effectively utilize GAI tools.

How to change performance evaluation practices?

Very connected to learning and development discussion, it seems quite important that companies calibrate the expectations for performance reviews. Some managers have noted that it becomes challenging to evaluate consultants uniformly as some extensively use GAI while others do not, leading to disparities in performance. Analysts have observed a similar pattern, noting that less technically proficient peers are already falling behind. *“But how can I insist that my consultants use GAI if it’s not a common and encouraged practice in the firm?”* one manager rightly questioned. Updating skills taxonomy, aligned with strategic priorities, and learning opportunities might help. Firms also need to establish productivity baselines and make it clear that the use of GAI is not only allowed but expected of consultants to remain competitive.

How increasing productivity will change consulting value proposition?

Productivity enhancements through GAI are already evident, reflecting its proficiency in tasks like producing convincing texts — a crucial component of consulting work. This efficiency is not only intuitive but has also been empirically supported by recent studies, such as those by (Dell’Acqua et al., 2023). Despite GAI tools like the GPT-4 model being in the early stages of development—with OpenAI’s CEO, Sam Altman, noting their limitations—the trajectory suggests that future generations will substantially improve productivity across all consulting levels (Fridman, n.d.).

The implications of this increased productivity, however, present a complex landscape for consulting firms. As productivity rises, firms may choose different strategies to leverage these gains. Some might improve employee well-being by reducing the long hours typical in the industry, thereby attracting talent previously deterred by the demanding culture. Others might opt for workforce reductions, maintaining traditional working hours and value propositions, reminiscent of the recent tech industry layoffs led by Twitter (Stringer, 2024). Alternatively, firms that effectively harness GAI could expand their project capacity and, consequently, their revenue, potentially leading to increased hiring rather than layoffs.

For example, while firms like McKinsey and KPMG have implemented significant layoffs in 2023, BCG plans to expand its workforce by over 2000 employees and anticipates deriving 20% of its revenue from AI projects by 2024 (Anghel, 2024; O'Dwyer, 2023; Raval & Foy, 2024). These divergent approaches highlight the varied strategies within the industry and suggest a shift in how consulting firms position themselves in a market increasingly influenced by AI.

The strategy consulting firms adopt in response to productivity gains from GAI will significantly shape their value proposition to both employees and clients. As this technology evolves, it will be crucial for firms to carefully consider how they adapt their business models and internal practices to maintain a competitive edge in the transformed landscape of management consulting.

How would project workflow change?

The advent of GAI tools in MC workflows compels a reevaluation of established project methodologies. Traditionally, the initial assessment phase of client documents is a time-intensive process, often spanning from a few weeks to months. With GAI, this timeline could be condensed, challenging the conventional hourly rate billing practices. As projects accelerate, consulting firms may need to consider alternative billing models, such as value-based or milestone-based schemes, which better capture the efficiencies GAI introduces.

Furthermore, GAI's ability to process large volumes of data more adeptly than humans necessitates the development of robust validation and quality control protocols for AI-generated content. Ensuring the integrity and accuracy of these insights before they reach the client is

critical, potentially shifting the consultant's role from routine data analysis and report generation to more strategic oversight and client relationship management.

These shifts in workflow and roles open up several areas for discussion: How will these changes manifest within different types of consulting engagements? What impacts could they have on the industry's value proposition to clients? As consultants move away from traditional tasks and towards higher-level strategic functions, the industry may see a transformation not just in the scope of work but also in how consulting services are perceived and valued by clients.

7. Limitations and future research

While this study provides valuable insights into the adoption and impact of generative AI in the consulting industry, it is subject to several limitations that require careful consideration.

First, the limitations of the study are directly related to the chosen research method, qualitative interviews, which provide few generalizable findings and struggle to cover a large enough sample to provide accurate statistical results (Adams, 2015).

The convenience sample selected by the author through his personal network is not completely diverse, despite efforts to speak with consultants from various backgrounds. The predominance of male participants and those in managerial positions or higher, coupled with the underrepresentation of female consultants, limits the diversity of perspectives captured. This bias is critical as it may omit different experiences and views on the use of GAI at different levels of expertise within the consulting industry. The study's findings are also based on interviews with one or two consultants per firm. Although most of the firms in the sample are global in scope, consultants are predominantly based in a particular market, typically Europe or the Middle East (UAE and Saudi Arabia), which may influence attitudes towards GAI and its use. The leading AI market, such as the US, was only covered by a single interview, and China was not covered at all in this study.

Selection bias also affects the results of the study, as all respondents reported prior familiarity with GAI. This method likely favors consultants who are more positive about the technology and excludes those who may be critical or indifferent. No participants admitted to a lack of

knowledge or discomfort with the technology, which may overestimate the actual readiness and commitment to GAI within their firms. Another limitation of this study is the potential influence of social desirability bias (Bergen & Labonté, 2020). This bias occurs when participants, knowing their responses are recorded, may alter their answers to appear more socially acceptable. This could impact the authenticity of the data, as participants might refrain from expressing true opinions or behaviors. Lastly, the research might have some translation bias, arising from the use of automated tools like generative AI (e.g., ChatGPT, DeepL) to translate interview responses from Russian into English. These tools, while efficient, may not capture linguistic nuances, cultural contexts, or colloquial expressions accurately. This could lead to misinterpretations or distortions in the data, impacting the study's overall validity.

Future research should aim for a more balanced approach, perhaps by integrating quantitative methods to complement the qualitative findings, and by broadening the participant base to include a more diverse demographic and geographic profile, as well as different types of MC firms. As another path for future studies, author sees continuing collaboration between academic institutions and consultancies, similar to rare experimental studies of BCG with Harvard Business School, or MIT with Accenture (Dell'Acqua et al., 2023; Gosline, 2024).

Such efforts would enhance the generalizability of the findings and provide a more comprehensive understanding of global GAI adoption patterns in management consulting. These considerations highlight the dynamic and complex nature of GAI technology adoption in professional settings and underscore the need for continued and nuanced exploration of this evolving field.

8. Conclusion

The advent of GAI heralds a significant transformation in the consulting industry, yet there are compelling reasons to remain optimistic about its future. Consultants are known for their adaptability (Klarner et al., 2013) and often acting as change agents for their clients (Cerruti et al., 2019). This nature of job positions them better than many other knowledge workers to embrace changes and integrate new technologies into their workflows. Their ability to learn

rapidly and accumulate diverse expertise makes them invaluable in navigating the complex landscapes introduced by GAI.

Moreover, the executives of consulting firms have a track record of steering through the complex transformations of their clients' industries. These experiences have not only honed their skills in managing change but also provided them with invaluable insights into the dynamics of technological adoption and integration. This reservoir of experience is a beacon of hope, suggesting that consulting firms are not only equipped to manage their own transformation in response to GAI but are also uniquely qualified to guide their clients through similar upheavals.

As GAI continues to evolve, it offers consulting firms the opportunity to redefine their value propositions, emphasizing strategic oversight, and deeper, more meaningful client engagements. The potential for increased efficiency and enhanced capabilities promises to elevate the consulting practice, enabling consultants to offer more innovative solutions and insights than ever before.

In light of these developments, the advent of GAI should be regarded not only as a challenge, but also as an opportunity for growth and innovation in the consulting industry. It offers the author hope that consulting firms will be able to dodge another technological disruption and can expect to remain as relevant and in demand by their clients as ever.

9. Disclosure statement

This study was conducted with the utmost adherence to academic integrity and ethical research standards. The author declares that there were no conflicts of interest influencing the research process. This research received no specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors. The author has no financial or personal relationships with other people or organizations that could inappropriately influence or bias the content of the paper.

The author conducted a comprehensive review of both academic and non-academic sources related to generative AI to inform the research process. This review aimed to integrate a broad spectrum of insights and perspectives into the analysis, ensuring a well-rounded understanding of the subject matter. The selection of sources was rigorous and aimed at covering the most relevant and recent contributions to the field of generative AI, particularly those pertinent to its application in management consulting. The perspectives and conclusions presented in this study are solely those of the author, derived from the data collected and analyzed independently.

This study incorporated the GAI tool, ChatGPT-4, to facilitate brainstorming, structuring ideas, and refining the writing style. It is important to note that while ChatGPT was instrumental in these processes, all data, sources, and content generated were meticulously verified by the author. This step was essential to ensure the accuracy of the information and to mitigate any potential discrepancies or factual errors commonly associated with outputs from GAI tools.

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Appendix

Questionnaire

Questionnaire used for most interviews conducted with consultants from large global consulting firms. Questionnaires for freelancers and representatives of small firms were slightly modified to reflect the nature of the consultants' work.

Current state:

1. Can you describe a time when you were introduced to a new gen.AI technology or tool in your professional or personal life? How did you approach learning and integrating it into your routine at the beginning?
2. After more than a year since the boom of ChatGPT, how has your company adapted to the LLM (large language models) technology? In particular
 - a. What are the firm's official rules and policies regarding the use of ChatGPT-like tools?
 - b. Has the firm stuck with any particular AI tool? (e.g. partnered with ChatGPT or developed an in-house tool). Can you describe this tool if it is the case?
 - c. In what areas is the use of AI permitted?
 - d. Does the firm have to label work that is wholly or partially produced by AI?
 - e. Will any AI-specific roles be created? (e.g. "prompt engineers", new Gen AI business units)
 - f. How does the company approach employee training?
3. How do you rate the clarity and efficiency of your firm's efforts to adapt the consulting profession to the emerging AI era?
4. What is the culture/attitude of you and your co-workers towards Gen AI? (e.g. if the use of AI is met with despair) Does your company conduct surveys to measure such sentiments among employees?
5. How can Gen-AI tools be used and what tasks can they perform? Please describe the most important and useful use cases.
 - a. How often do you perform the described tasks with AI assistance (one time vs. recurring)?
6. How do you feel (estimate) the productivity gains from the use of Gen-AI tools by consultants today?
7. Are there any internal forums for sharing best practice on the use of gen AI?
8. Have clients adjusted their expectations over the last year, perhaps because they are aware that consultants are also using AI? How has project delivery and client satisfaction changed?

Future state

9. What risks do you see in nearest future posed by GenAI
 - a. the consulting industry in general
 - b. you personally
10. Now please imagine your version of the future of technology in the context of consulting in say the next 10 years:
 - a. What tasks will it cover? What would be left for humans?
 - b. Will its use be promoted / encouraged or on the contrary prohibited?
 - c. How different would consulting be from what you and industry do today?

List of conducted interviews

Table 4. List of conducted interviews

#	Company	Experience in management consulting	Region	Date	Duration
1	Big-4	15+ years, Director	Middle East	6 March 2024	00:38:40
2	Freelance management consultant	5-10 years, Manager	Middle East	11 March 2024	00:28:32
3	Global consulting	5-10 years, Manager	Middle East	13 March 2024	00:59:21
4	Specialized global boutique	10-15 years, Senior Manager	APAC	13 March 2024	00:46:56
5	Big-4	5-10 years, Manager	UK	17 March 2024	00:50:44
6	Big-3	5-10 years, Associate	EU	18 March 2024	00:37:23
7	Global consulting	15+ years, Principal	EU	21 March 2024	00:31:10
8	Global consulting	2-5 years, Consultant	Middle East	23 March 2024	00:54:19
9	Small consulting	15+ years, Partner	Middle East	24 March 2024	Not recorded
10	Big-3	5 years, GAI coach and knowledge analyst	EU	25 March 2024	00:47:27

11	Global consulting	2-5 years, Consultant	EU	27 March 2024	00:50:30
12	Big-4	5-10 years, Senior Manager	EU	29 March 2024	00:45:00
13	Big-4	10-15 years, Senior Manager	Middle East	31 March 2024	00:31:51
14	Specialized global boutique	15+ years, Senior Manager	APAC	04 April 2024	00:31:46
15	Global consulting	5-10 years, Manager	EU	19 April 2024	00:58:14
16	Big-4	2-5 years, Senior analyst	EU	19 April 2024	00:33:55
17	Freelancer	2-5 years, Senior analyst	CIS	19 April 2024	00:34:45
18	Small consulting	2-5 years, Analyst	EU	21 April 2024	00:32:48
19	Big-3	5-10 years, Principal	Middle East	23 April 2024	00:42:39
20	Big-3	5-10 years, Manager	Middle East	24 April 2024	Not recorded
21	Big-3	10-15 years, Manager	US	12 May 2024	Not recorded